

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17409664

Factors Militating Electrical Electronics Technology Education Students' Participation in Practical Activities in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State.

¹Ugoji, P.C., ¹Ezebunwa, Austin Chisa., & ¹Umiaghe Moses .A.,

¹Department of Electrical/Electronics Technology Education
Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study investigated factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Three research questions and null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 50 electrical electronics technology education lecturers from three tertiary institutions in Rivers State namely; Rivers State University (RSU), Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) and Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku, Rivers State and 87 electrical electronics technology education final year students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The researchers adopted the entire population hence, there was no need for sampling. The instrument tagged "Factors Militating Electrical Electronics Technology Education Students' Participation in Practical Activities" was used and validated by three experts in the field. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient which resulted in .85 reliability coefficient. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while z-test statistical tool was used in testing the hypothesis. Mean values < 3.00 were rejected, while mean values ≥ 3.00 were accepted. Also, calculated hypotheses values $<$ table values were accepted while calculated hypotheses \geq table values were rejected. The findings revealed that students lack of interest, lack of motivation, incompetence, non-retraining of teachers on new equipment and advancing technology for practical activities, limited resources, facilities and funding, amongst others are factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It was recommended that management of tertiary institutions should train lecturers on new equipment that will be useful in teaching students modern skills in order to build students interest to effectively participate in practical activities in the workshops.

Keywords: Activity, Education, Electrical, Electronics, Factor, Militate, Participation, Practical, Student & Technology

INTRODUCTION

Technical education is an education programme that prepares people for specific trades, craft, technical or a professional position in engineering, accountancy, nursing, medicine, architecture, pharmacy, law and so on. The National Policy on Education cited in Ojimba (2013) defined technical education as that aspect of education which leads to the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge. Also, Ochogba and Deebom (2019) defined technical education as the education that provides the requisite skills needed for self employment or for gainful employment in industries. Those aspects of education process involving the acquisition of practical skills, attitude, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Because technical education is designed to provide different skills and knowledge, different programmes are offered which include Electrical/electronics technology education.

Electrical and electronics technology education is a course in technical education that equips individuals with specific skills, knowledge, and attributes/attitudes to enable them maintain, repair and construct basic electrical/electronics systems in Practice (Nweke, 2017 in Attamah & Dauda, 2017). Electrical and electronics technology is an aspect of Technical Education programme offered in Government Technical Colleges and tertiary institutions such as universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education with the aim of producing Electrical and electronics technologists, technicians, craftsmen and teachers (Oluwalola, 2019). Electrical electronics technology is a programme that is designed in tertiary institutions to train individuals who will serve as technologists in electrical or electronics related industries or be able to create employment by being self-reliant (Amadi et al, 2021).

According to the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2011 in Lawal, et al., 2023), the main goal of Electrical/electronics technology is to produce competent Electrical/electronics technicians and technologists who are skilled to conduct various types of electrical and electronics installations, diagnose, repairs, and maintenance. Basically, electrical electronics technology equips students with knowledge, skills and attitudes needed for performance in the field of electrical electronics and for gainful employment (Attamah & Dauda, 2017). However, skills acquisition cannot be fully achieved with poor students' participation in practical activities.

Practical activities is seen as any science teaching and learning activity which at some point involves the students working individually or in small groups, in observing or manipulating objects, to build up understanding (Millar, 2009). Practical learning refers to learning that is whole—that involves head, heart, and hands working in harmony. It occurs when learners experience and navigate real world challenges and apply their knowledge in a range of settings. Practical activities are essential in electrical/electronics technology education as they provide students with hands-on experience and the opportunity to apply theoretical concepts to real-world problems, thereby enhancing their understanding and retention of the material. By engaging in practical activities, students can develop critical skills such as troubleshooting, problem-solving, and experimentation, which are crucial for success in the field of electrical/electronics technology. Attesting to this, Nwosu et al. (2020) started that practical activities are essential for the development of problem-solving skills in electrical/electronics technology education.

However, despite the significance of practical activities in electrical/electronics technology education, Okeke & Eze (2013) lamented that electrical/electronics technology education students do not participate actively in practical activities. Also, Eze et al. (2019) noted that the lack of practical experience among electrical/electronics technology education students is a major challenge facing the field. The study emphasized the need for educators to design and implement practical activities that challenge students and help them develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills. This provide additional evidence to support the claim that electrical/electronics technology education students often do not participate actively in practical activities, and that this lack of participation can hinder their development of technical skills and competencies.

Some of the factors which hampers the participation of students are socio-economic status of parents, environment, attitude of family, lack of adequate material and facilities (Edosa, 2020). Also, Aprieliava et al (2021) found that motivational structure, desire to study, self expression, self fulfilment of set goals, personal leadership, relationship with teachers and classmates, self development, creativity, self efficacy, openness, self confidence, self perception and self attitude, among others are some of the factors affecting students participation in school activities. These factors could be responsible for ineffective participation of electrical electronics technology education students' in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Hence it is worthwhile for the researchers to carry out a study or investigate the factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

One of the objectives of electrical electronics technology education in tertiary institutions is to ensure adequate practical performances of students in the workshop. However, this expected performance has been observed to be poor in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It was recorded by Total E&P and Shell Petroleum Development Company that about 80% of electronic technology employees from Rivers State tertiary institutions cannot perform basic electronics troubleshooting before employment (Amadi et al, 2021). If this is not checked, the nation's economic growth will recess further.

According to a study by Okoro et al. (2018), the incompetence of electrical/electronics technology education students in Nigeria can be attributed to their ineffective participation in practical activities, which hinders their ability to develop the necessary skills and competencies required in the field during their training. The study found that many students in electrical/electronics technology education programs in Nigeria do not participate actively in practical activities, leading to a lack of hands-on experience and a subsequent inability to apply theoretical concepts to real-world problems. Similarly, studies by Eze et al. (2019) and Nwosu et al (2020) noted that the lack of practical experience among electrical/electronics technology education students is a major challenge facing the field, and it is a significant contributor to their incompetence. This in turn affects the society creating an increased crime rate and social disorder which can negatively affect the economic output of the nation as well as the human resource strength, and economic productivity of the nation at large. Hence the need for an in-depth analysis on the factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Specifically, this study sought to:

1. Examine students' psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. Ascertain societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

1. What are the psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. What are the societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and final year students on the psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and final year students on the societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The area of the study was the tertiary institutions in Rivers State which offers electrical electronics technology education as a discipline which includes; Rivers State University (RSU), Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) and Federal College of Education (Technical) (FCET), Omoku. The population comprised 50 electrical electronics technology education lecturers from the three tertiary institutions in Rivers State; which consisted of 30 lecturers in Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku, 12 lecturers from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and 8 lecturers from Rivers State University. As well as 87 electrical electronics technology education final year students consisting of 22 students from Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, 30 students from Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and 35 students from Rivers State University. Due to the fact that the population was small and manageable, the researcher adopted the entire population as the sample size, hence there was no sampling technique used and the sample size amounted to 137 respondents. Structured survey questionnaire titled "Factors Militating Electrical Electronics Technology Education Students' Participation in Practical Activities" (FMEETESPPA) served as the instrument for data collection. The instrument was structured in the pattern of 5 point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA-5), Agree (A-4), Undecided (U-3), Disagree (D-2) and Strongly Disagree (SD-1). The face validity of the instrument was ascertained by 3 experts in electrical electronics education technology in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. More so, the instrument was subjected to test of reliability using Cronbach Alpha

Reliability Coefficient method. The reliability coefficient established was .85. Copies of the instrument were administered and retrieved by the researchers. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test was used to test the hypotheses at .05 level of significance. Mean values less than 3.00 were rejected while mean scores equal or greater than 3.00 were accepted. The null hypothesis was rejected if the z-calculated exceeds the z-table; otherwise, the null hypothesis was accepted (if z-cal is greater than z-crit reject the null hypothesis, whereas if z-cal is less than z-crit accept the stated null hypothesis).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on Psychological Factors Militating Participation in Practical Activities

S/N	Psychological factors	Lecturers (n ₁ =50)		Students (n ₂ =87)			Decision
		\bar{x}_1	SD	Decision	\bar{x}_2	SD	
1.	Fear of equipment damage	4.08	1.12	Agree	4.32	1.25	Agree
2.	Lack of familiarity with tools and equipment	4.12	1.14	Agree	3.66	1.39	Agree
3.	Perceived risk of injury	3.94	1.23	Agree	4.08	1.25	Agree
4.	Lack of confidence	3.82	1.22	Agree	3.60	1.38	Agree
5.	Fear of making mistake	4.12	1.29	Agree	4.57	1.01	Agree
6.	Perceived lack of relevance	4.30	1.20	Agree	4.39	1.05	Agree
7.	Anxiety	3.48	1.40	Agree	4.33	1.03	Agree
8.	Fear of failure	4.02	1.33	Agree	4.16	1.22	Agree
9.	Lack of interest in practical activities	4.04	1.28	Agree	3.70	1.34	Agree
Grand Mean (GM) and SD		3.99	1.25		4.09	1.21	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 on the psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria shows that the mean scores by both groups for all the items were above 3.00, which is the acceptable mean value. Thus, all the factors listed are psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The closeness in the standard deviation which is 1.25 and 1.21 for lecturers and students respectively indicate homogeneity in the responses of the groups. Therefore, in answer to research question 1, the psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria include fear of equipment damage, lack of familiarity with tools and equipment, perceived risk of injury, lack of confidence, fear of making mistakes, perceived lack of relevance, anxiety, fear of failure and lack of interest in practical activities. This is in line with Aprieliava et al (2021) that found that motivational structure, desire to study, self expression, self fulfilment of set goals, personal leadership, relationship with teachers and classmates, self development, creativity, self efficacy, openness, self confidence, self perception and self attitude, among others are some of the factors affecting students participation in school activities.

Research Question 2: *What are the societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on Societal Factors Militating Participation in Practical Activities

S/N	Societal factors	Lecturers (n ₁ =50)		Students (n ₂ =87)			
		\bar{x}_1	SD	Decision	\bar{x}_2	SD	Decision
10.	Socioeconomic status of parents	4.44	1.00	Agree	3.65	1.48	Agree
11.	Family and community support	4.66	0.86	Agree	4.51	1.05	Agree
12.	Government policies and poor funding of technical education programme	4.44	0.82	Agree	4.65	0.93	Agree
13.	Societal attitude towards electrical electronic technology education	4.28	1.09	Agree	4.48	0.82	Agree
14.	Absence of role models	4.02	1.33	Agree	4.16	1.22	Agree
15.	Unavailability of job opportunities for electrical/electronics technology education graduates	4.04	1.28	Agree	3.70	1.34	Agree
16.	Societal values around hand skills and manual labour	4.16	1.28		4.72	0.65	
17.	Social vices	3.90	1.18	Agree	4.65	.93	Agree
Grand Mean (GM) and SD		4.24	1.11		4.32	1.05	

Table 2 on the societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria shows that the mean scores by both groups for all the items were above 3.00, which is the acceptable mean value. Thus, all the factors listed are societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria. The closeness in the standard deviation which is 1.25 and 1.21 for lecturers and students respectively indicate homogeneity in the responses of the groups. Therefore, in answer to research question 1, the societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria include: socioeconomic status of parents, family and community support, government policies and poor funding of technical education programme, societal attitude towards electrical electronics technology education, absence of role models in technical education, unavailability of job opportunities for electrical/electronics technology education graduates, societal values around skills and manual labour and social vices. This is in agreement with Edosa (2020) who found that some of the factors which hampers the participation of students are socio-economic status of parents, environment, attitude of family, lack of adequate material and facilities.

Hypotheses

Table 1: z-test Analysis on the Factors Militating Students' Participation in Practical Activities in Tertiary Institutions in Rivers State, Nigeria

Hypothesis	Category	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
H0 ₁	Lecturers	50	3.99	1.25	135	.46	1.96	NS
	Students	87	4.09	1.21				
H0 ₂	Lecturers	50	4.24	1.11	135	.41	1.96	NS
	Students	87	4.32	1.05				

The result in Table 3 shows that z-cal for H0₁ was .46, which is less than the z-crit of 1.96, meaning that H0₁ was accepted. Thus, there was no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and final year students on the psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Also, the result in Table 3 shows that z-cal for H0₂ was .41, which is less than z-crit of 1.96, meaning that H0₂ was accepted. Therefore, there was no significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and final year students on the societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

CONCLUSIONS

This study concludes that fear of equipment damage, lack of familiarity with tools and equipment, perceived risk of injury, lack of confidence, fear of making mistake, perceived lack of relevance, anxiety and fear of failure are some of the psychological factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. More so, socioeconomic status of parents, family and community support, government policies and poor funding of technical education programme, societal attitude towards electrical electronics technology education, absence of role models, unavailability of job opportunities for electrical/electronics technology education graduate, societal values around hand skills and manual labour and social vices are some of the societal factors militating electrical electronics technology education students' participation in practical activities in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Workshop technologists in technical education should organize orientation for new students in order to allay their fears in the use of workshop equipment which will in turn ensure effective participation in practical activities.
2. Technical institutions should partner with host communities, government, industries and Non-Governmental Organizations so as to sensitize the people about the importance of technical education programme and to solicit support for the development of technical education department.

REFERENCES

Amadi, D.N., Nwokorie, C.C., & Opara, J.A. (2020). Assessment of the performance of electrical/electronics technology education graduates from tertiary institutions in Rivers State. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 13(2), 15-25.

Aprieliava, I.V., Demchenko, V.A., Kovalevska, A.V., Kovalevska, T.Y., & Hladum, T.S. (2021). Psychological factors influencing on the motivation to study of students of TEL. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20511/pyr2021.v9Nspe2.993>

- Attamah, C.E., & Dauda, D.I. (2017). Employers' perception of the applied skills of Nigeria Certificate of Education graduates of electrical-electronics technology in Nigeria public and private organization. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 7(6), 12-23
- Edosa, J.T. (2020). The factors affecting students participation in physical education and sport programming Jitu preparatory school, Nekemte City, East Wollega, Oromia Ethiopia. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 25(9), 40-44.
- Eze, C.E., Okeke, E.N., & Nwosu, P.C. (2019). Challenges facing electrical/electronics technology education in Nigeria: A study of students' practical experience. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(2), 10-20.
- Lawal, H., Idris, A., Jido, S.H., Saleh, J., & Abduaziz, N. (2023). Skills competency among electrical/electronics technology undergraduate students in tertiary institutions in Kano State. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 10(7), 20-25
- Millar, R. (2009). *Analysing practical activities to assess and improve effectiveness: The practical activity analysis inventory*. Center for innovation and research in science education
- Nwosu, P.C., Eze, C.E., & Akpan, E.S. (2020). Developing problem-solving skills in electrical/electronics technology education: The role of practical activities. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 12(1), 15-25.
- Ochogba, C.O., & Deebom. M.T. (2019). The role of plant layout in the implementation of technical education programme in Rivers State, Nigeria. *British International Journal of Education and Social Sciences*, 6(1), 20-25.
- Ojimba, D.P. (2013). Technical and vocational education imperatives for socio-economic and political stability in Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(19), 9-18
- Okeke, E.N., & Eze, C.E. (2013). Challenges facing the teaching and learning of electrical/electronics technology in Nigerian universities. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 5(1), 1-15.
- Okoro, O.C., Amuzie, C.U., & Okoro, E.C. (2018). Incompetence of electrical/electronics technology education students in Nigeria: A study of the role of practical activities. *Journal of Technical Education and Training*, 10(1), 20-30.
- Oluwalola, F. (2019). Business studies and employability skills development in junior secondary schools. *Journal of Education Policy*, 21-23